

Pentoxifylline

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ABSTRACT

Pentoxifylline is a methylxanthine derivative used to treat intermittent claudication caused by chronic occlusive arterial disease of the limbs. Other off-label indications are cerebrovascular disease, Behcet's disease, congestive heart failure, vascular disorder of inner ear, venous stasis ulcer of leg, diabetes mellitus (adjunct therapy, diabetic nephropathy), non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and Peyronie's disease. Because of the antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, immune-modulatory, bronchodilator and respiratory supportive effects, protective roles in organ failures, along with its main functions means better circulation-oxygenation properties, low price and safety, pentoxifylline is now being investigated in a clinical trial as a multipurpose and generally-safe adjuvant therapy for COVID-19 patients.

INTRODUCTION

Pentoxifylline (PTX) is a methylxanthine derivative used to treat intermittent claudication caused by chronic occlusive arterial disease of the limbs. PTX modulates the rheological properties of blood and also has both anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Although

originally developed to treat intermittent claudication, a form of exertion-induced leg pain common in patients with peripheral arterial disease, PTX has been investigated for its possible use in diverse conditions, including osteoradionecrosis, diabetic kidney disease, and generally any condition associated with fibrosis. More recently, PTX has been suggested as a possible treatment for COVID-19-induced pulmonary complications due to its ability to regulate the production of inflammatory cytokines¹. PTX acts primarily by increasing red blood cell deformability, by reducing blood viscosity and by decreasing the potential for platelet aggregation and thrombus formation².

BEHCET'S DISEASE

Behcet's disease is an inflammatory disorder of unknown cause, characterized by recurrent oral aphthous ulcers, genital ulcers, uveitis, and skin lesions. All these common manifestations are self-limiting except for the ocular attacks. Appenzeller S. and Hazel E. reported a patient with ocular involvement secondary to Behcet's disease which was corticosteroid dependent and refractory to azathioprine treatment. PTX was added with amelioration of inflammation.

Authors concluded that PTX may be a useful treatment option in patients with Behcet's disease, where other immunosuppressives have failed or are contra-indicated³.

VASCULAR DISEASES

PTX has been investigated and approved in **cerebrovascular disease** (600 to 1200 mg/day orally; off-label dosage), **congestive heart failure** (400 mg orally 3 times daily for 6 months; given with standard regimens of digoxin, diuretics, and ACE inhibitors; off-label dosage), **intermittent claudication** (400 mg orally 3 times daily with meals; efficacy has been demonstrated in studies with a duration of 6 months), **vascular disorder of inner ear** (1600 mg/day orally in 2 to 4 divided doses; off-label dosage) and **venous stasis ulcer of leg** (400 mg orally 3 times per day; off-label dosage)⁴.

DIABETES MELLITUS

The effects of pentoxifylline on proteinuria, renal function, glucose control, and inflammatory parameters were investigated in a prospective, randomized double-blind, placebo-controlled, multi-center study. A total of 174 patients with type 2 diabetes and albuminuria (>30 mg/g of creatinine) who were taking the recommended dosage of ACEI or ARB for >6 months and receiving conventional therapy for diabetes were

randomly assigned to receive PTX (1200 mg, daily; n = 87) or a placebo (n = 87) for 6 months. The percentage changes in proteinuria from baseline in the pentoxifylline and placebo groups were a decrease of 23% and 4%, respectively ($p = 0.012$). In addition, significant reductions in fasting plasma glucose, glycated hemoglobin, and insulin resistance according to the homeostasis model assessment were observed in the pentoxifylline group compared to those in the placebo group. However there was no significant difference in serum tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α between the groups. Authors concluded that PTX is a potential therapeutic alternative for treating diabetes and diabetic nephropathy⁵.

Off-label dosage for PTX as an adjunct therapy in diabetes mellitus is 400 mg orally 3 times daily and for proteinuria reduction in diabetes mellitus is 400 mg once or trice daily⁴.

COVID-19

The antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, immune-modulatory, bronchodilator and respiratory supportive effects and protective roles in organ failures of PTX, along with its main functions means better circulation-oxygenation properties, low price and safety, make it a promising drug to be considered for COVID-19 treatment, especially as an adjuvant therapy in combination with other drugs⁶.

Because of the potential antiviral effects on severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and hemorrheologic properties for a better circulation and oxygenation, and its unique effects on immune modulation, inflammation and oxidative stress, PTX is now being investigated in a clinical trial as a multipurpose and generally-safe adjuvant therapy for COVID-19 patients⁷.

OTHER

Other off-label indications for PTX use are non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (1200 mg orally once daily for 3 to 12 months) and early chronic phase of Peyronie's disease (400 mg orally two or three times daily)⁴.

CONCLUSION

Pentoxifylline is a methylxanthine derivative used to treat intermittent claudication caused by chronic occlusive arterial disease of the limbs. Other off-label indications are cerebrovascular disease, Behcet's disease, congestive heart failure, vascular disorder of inner ear, venous stasis ulcer of leg, diabetes mellitus (adjunct therapy, diabetic nephropathy), non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and Peyronie's disease. Because of the antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, immune-modulatory, bronchodilator and respiratory supportive effects, protective roles in organ failures, along with its main

functions means better circulation-oxygenation properties, low price and safety, pentoxifylline is now being investigated in a clinical trial as a multipurpose and generally-safe adjuvant therapy for COVID-19 patients.

Pentoxifylline might also be considered as prophylactic and protective therapy during the COVID-19 pandemic era in patients who already have above-mentioned indications for its use.

REFERENCES

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